

Zootechnical Performance of Boer Cross Goat Populations in Grazing System in Northern Burundi

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Abstract

This study aimed to estimate the zootechnical performance of kids resulting from the crossing between indigenous female goats and Billy goat Boers in the pasture system in the northern region of Burundi. Zootechnical parameters were monthly recorded from birth to breeding age in the form of longitudinal monitoring and concerned mortality rates, live weight, and body measurements. The results showed that the mortality rates for indigenous kids and kids crossed Boers goats were 15.6% and 23.5% respectively. For each category of weaned kids' mortality rates are higher during the rainy season with 18.1% and 9.4% for Boer-crossed kids and indigenous kids respectively. The live weights were 2.7 ± 0.52 kg at birth; 5.6 ± 0.35 kg at 1 month; 8.1 ± 1.35 kg at 3 months; 13.2 ± 0.91 kg at 6 months and 20.4 ± 1.21 kg at 9 months for the group of crossbred kids Boers against 1.8 ± 0.38 kg, 3.8 ± 0.12 kg, 6.8 ± 0.12 kg, 9.3 ± 0.23 kg and 13.4 ± 0.23 kg for the group of indigenous kids' goats at same age. Body measurements in the group of Boer crossbred kids were 67.2 ± 1.5 cm for thoracic perimeter; 54.4 ± 1.4 cm for height at the withers; 57.7 ± 1.6 cm for body length and 21.9 ± 0.1 cm depth of the chest against 59.1 ± 1.9 cm, 47.2 ± 2.1 cm; 54.8 ± 0.9 cm and 19.6 ± 0.7 cm for the group of indigenous kid' s goats. A highly significant difference was observed between the two genetic groups with a larger difference in the group of Boer-crossed kid' s goats and indigenous kids of 3 months. This study concluded that the crossbreeding program between Boer goats and local female goats could be effective if accompanied by a careful selection of native female goats.

Keywords: Billy Boer, Indigenous Goats, Live Weight, Measurements, Mortality.

Introduction

In major developing countries, goat farming is one of the largest livestock sectors, and about 35% of the world goat population is found in Africa (Skapetas and Bampidis, 2016). In Burundi, the goat is assimilated into the current account of the farmer by helping to solve the socio-economic challenges of rural communities (Ibnel Bachy *et al.*, 2015). The number of goats is estimated at 3.2 million heads, against 3.4 million for poultry, 1.1 for cattle, 0.8 for pigs, and 0.5 for sheep (MINEAGRIE, 2017). Although the goat is the highest-raised animal, its productivity remains very low to ensure food security and the well-being of farmers (Devendra, 2010).

Two main reasons explain this low productivity: (1) the goats are mainly bred extensively by farmers established on marginal lands and (2) their practice of negative selection based on the sale of more vigorous kids promotes the evolution of genetic traits low performing individuals (Rege *et al.*, 2011). However, it is possible to increase goats' productivity by implementing a genetic improvement program, as is done in many countries.

Subsequently, the government of Burundi has initiated genetic improvement programs based on the importation of purebred Boer goats from Tanzania and Uganda since 2005, (MINEAGRIE, 2017) to improve the productivity of female indigenous goats through crossbreeding (Manirakiza *et al.*, 2020a). The introduction of Boer blood in the goat population in Burundi could directly improve the weight growth of hybrid kids and indirectly the phenotypic traits of native goats (Manirakiza *et al.*, 2020b).

The growth performance and the different traits related to body measurements from birth to reproduction age (9 months of age) of hybrid kids compared to indigenous type kid's goats are until now unknown. Thus, the objective of this study is to evaluate the productivity of hybrid kid's goat resulting from the cross between local breed goat females and purebred Billy Boer in terms of mortality rate, live weight, and body measurements, especially in three densely populated Northern provinces of Burundi.

Material and Methods

Study Area

The study was conducted in the region located in the north of Burundi from 1400 to 2500 m altitude, comprising three agro-ecological zones of Buyenzi, Mugamba, and Bugesera (Bidou *et al.*, 1991). In this region, the dry season extends 3 to 4 months per year, and annual rainfall and temperatures are 1500 to 2000 mm/year and 10 to 20°C respectively. In particular, the region of Buyenzi is characterized by greater human demographic pressure with more than 300 inhabitants/km² (Ministry of the Interior, 2010).

Feed Resources

The animals are permanently kept on natural rangelands composed essentially of the following grasses and legumes: *Imperata cylindrica*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Hypparrhenia rufa*, *Eleusina indica*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Lantana camara*. Cultivated fodder species consist of *Trypsacum laxum*, *Setaria sphacelata*, *Pennisetum purpureum*, *Calliandra calothyrsus*, and *Leucaena leucocephala*. The rangelands have low pastoral value but the use of concentrate feeds or mineral supplements is not common in this region.

Animal Selection

The data used to carry out this study was collected on a population of 64 hybrid kids born from the cross between local breed females and imported Boer goats and 86 kids born from indigenous females and males. The Indigenous goat population reared in this region is related to the East African Dwarf Goat (Manirakiza *et al.*, 2020a). Twelve Boer goats were identified in six communes covering the study area. Each Billy Boer goat was kept in an individual room and fed semi-intensively. Pregnant females were selected from the database of natural mating records while the dates of birth and death of the kids were recorded by communal veterinarians in each commune. Females in anestrus within 45 days of mating were considered to be pregnant. Native pregnant goats were revealed by breeders during the preliminary investigation. A total of 80 female goats, including 40 mated with Boer goats and 40 others mated with locally reared goats, were identified for a longitudinal survey.

Collection of Data

Weighings and measurements were made on 98 Boer crossbred kids and 77 indigenous kids using a suspended circular spring scale and tape measure. Measurement and weighing operations were carried out by a community animal health worker attached to each hill. Each kid born was weighed within 12 hours after birth and successively after 1 month, 3 months, 6 months, and 9 months. The kids were weaned at 3 months of age and the mating age of female goats was fixed at 9 months. The pre-weaning mortality rate of the kids was given by the percentage of kids dead at the time of weaning (3rd month), while the post-weaning mortality rate was calculated by considering the kids who died from 4 to 9 months. Measurements were taken early in the morning before grazing time. Each animal was weighed and measurements were taken following the recommendations of Fajemilehin and Salako (2008).

Data Analysis

The data collected was recorded in an Excel spreadsheet (Microsoft Office 2013). Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 20 software (SPSS 2000, Chicago, IL, USA). Analysis based on linear mixed-effects models (PROC. MIXED) for repeated measures was carried out to study the variation in weights at selected ages. The ANOVA, Scheffé test was used to compare the average weights, death rate and body measurements between the two genetic groups of goats. Significant differences were declared at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

Live Weight

The results presented in Table 1 showed that the Boer crossbred kids have a significantly higher weight than the local ones at 30 days from birth ($p < 0.05$). Sex and genetic group did not significantly influence the weight of kids at birth ($p > 0.05$) despite the superior birth weight of Boer crossbred kids. The effects of the genetic group become significant from the age of 1 month ($p < 0.05$). At this age, sex has no significant influence on weight within each genetic group ($p > 0.05$).

At 90 days of age, Boer crossbred kids had a significantly higher weight than native-breed kids ($p < 0.05$). Also, a significant difference between male and female Boer crossed kid's goats on the one hand and native male and female kid's goats on the other hand was observed.

At 180 days of age, Boer crossbred kids had a significantly higher weight ($p < 0.05$) than local breed kid's goats. Within each genetic group, males were significantly heavier than females ($p < 0.05$).

At 270 days of age, the situation remains unchanged, but the weight of Boer-crossed female kids was not significantly different from that of Boer-crossed males ($p > 0.05$).

Table 1: Live weight of kids at different growth stages according to sex and genetic groups

Sources of variation	Weight at birth (kg)	Weight at 30 days (kg)	Weight at 90 days (kg)	Weight at 180 days (kg)	Weight at 270 days (kg)
Genetic group					
Boer crossbred kids (n=64)	2.7±0.52 ^a	5.6±0.35 ^a	8.1±1.35 ^a	13.2±0.91 ^a	20.4±1.21 ^a
Indigenous kids (n=86)	1.8±0.38 ^a	3.8±0.12 ^b	6.8±0.12 ^b	9.3±0.23 ^b	13.4±0.23 ^b
Sex					
Boer crossbred male	2.4±0.23 ^a	5.7±0.40 ^a	9.2±0.15 ^a	13.2±0.20 ^a	20.0±0.38 ^a
Boer crossbred female	2.1±0.42 ^a	5.0±0.43 ^a	7.9±0.27 ^b	12.6±0.82 ^b	21.2±0.42 ^b
Indigenous male	1.7±0.12 ^a	4.3±0.17 ^b	6.8±0.38 ^c	9.5±0.18 ^c	15.1±0.18 ^c
Indigenous female	1.4±0.61 ^a	4.1±0.12 ^b	6.3±0.18 ^d	8.87±0.18 ^d	14.31±0.18 ^c

^{abc} the values of the same column bearing different exponents are significantly different at $p < 5$

The results of this study revealed that Boer crossbred kids are born with a significantly higher live weight ($p < 0.05$) than native kids. In addition, some authors report that crossbreeding Boer males and local breed females improves

the birth weight of kids, compared to that of local kids (Browning and Leite-Browning, 2009).

Average live weight at birth (2.7 ± 0.52 kg) of Boer crossbred kids observed during the present study is higher than that found in other studies carried out in Lubumbashi (2.40 ± 0.31 kg) (Kalenga *et al.*, 2015) and Kenya (2.06 ± 0.4 kg) (Nsubuga, 1996).

However, the values of birth weight of kids observed in our study are much inferior to those found by Zhang *et al.* (2008) when the Boer crossbred kids (3.87 ± 0.85 kg) were reared in semi-intensive systems. This observation illustrates that the rearing system influences positively the live weight at animal birth.

Regarding the sex of kids, no significant difference in birth weight was observed between males and females ($p < 0.05$). This did not agree with that of authors who estimated that sex significantly influences birth weight (Browning and Leite-Browning, 2009).

Furthermore, the live weight of male kids, regardless of genetic group, is significantly higher than that of females from 3 to 6 months. Our results corroborate with those found in a study that revealed that sex could significantly influence the live weight of Boer x Alpine Malabari kids from the 6th month until the age of breeding (Jeeva *et al.*, 2011).

At breeding age (9 months), we observed that Boer crossbred kids weigh 7kg more than native kids. Particularly some factors as so as the higher feed efficiency of crossbred kids compared to that of kids of indigenous breeds could explain this superior live weight (Ademosum *et al.*, 1988). In addition, the superior live weight of crossbred descendants may be the result of the additive genetic effects of exotic males on their offspring (Kalenga *et al.*, 2015).

Generally, significant growth and body development of crossbred animals results from a combination of heterosis effects expressed by the parents (Rhone, 2005). A recent study reported that the birth weight of Boer crossbred kids at F1 showed a heterosis effect estimated to be 5% compared to the average of the parents (Kalenga *et al.*, 2015).

A positive correlation between the live weight of dams and the birth weight of their offspring regardless of litter size has been reported (Morand-Fehr, 1981). Thus, a selection program based on the live weight of native females should be made when starting cross-breeding projects with Boer males to benefit from a possible heterosis effect.

At the age of 9 months, females become slightly heavy (21.2 kg; $p > 0.05$) compared to male kids (20.0 kg) in the genetic group of Boer crossbred kids at the same age, an average live weight of indigenous kids' females remains inferior but not significant ($p > 0.05$) than that of intra-group males. From the above, some authors have confirmed that the male breed would considerably influence the living weight at all ages of offspring (Jeeva *et al.*, 2011). This would explain the superiority of Boer-crossed children compared to native children.

Death Rate

The results showed that 8 Boer crossbred kids (8.2%) and 5 native kids (6.5%) died before the weaning age. Death rates of kid's goats are particularly higher during the rainy season in groups of Boer crossbred kids. As shown in Table 2, the Boer crossbred kids (pre and post-weaning) were more vulnerable during the rainy period. Therefore, the death rates of kids were equivalent in all genetic groups of kid goats born in the dry season.

The death rate for Boer crossbred kids (23.5%) is higher than that observed for native-breed kids (15.6%). In a study conducted by Manirakiza *et al.* (2020a), the mortality rate for kids under 1 year was estimated at 27.2% for herds of indigenous and crossbred kids and at 18.3% for herds of indigenous kids exclusively. For these authors, the main causes of death in kids are gastrointestinal parasites (56.5%), pneumonia (12.4%), and diseases caused by ticks (12.2%).

The death rates observed in the context of our study are higher than that found in Uganda (11%) in the case of crosses between Boer goats and females of the "East African dwarf goat" type (Nsubuga, 1996). Digestive disorders and the inability of mothers to take care of twins during their first days of life are the causes of the deaths mentioned by this author. Moreover, it has been reported that mothers of several litters tend to refuse access to the udder of the last newborns in the litter (Lehloenyia *et al.*, 2005). This situation compromises the intake of the first food

(colostrum) which guarantees the immunity of newborns.

Table 2: Number of Boer crossbred and indigenous kid's goats born and died from birth to weaning ages during the dry and rainy seasons

		Dry season	Rainy season	Total
Kids born		55	120	175
Boer crossbred kids		33(60%)	65(54.2%)	98
Indigenous kids		22(40%)	55(45.8%)	77
Death rates		8(14.5%)	27(22.5%)	35(20%)
Pre-weaning	Boer crossbred kids	1(12.5%)	7(25.9%)	8(22.9%)
	Indigenous kids	2(25%)	3(11.2%)	5(14.3%)
Post-weaning	Boer crossbred kids	3(37.5%)	12(44.4%)	15(42.8%)
	Indigenous kids	2(25%)	5(18.5%)	7(20%)

Problems adapting to extensive farming conditions in the humid tropical region are also major causes of mortality in hybrid kids (Manirakiza *et al.*, 2020b). It should be noted that the adaptability of Hybrid kids to environmental variations increases with their body development (Zhang *et al.*, 2009). During our study, a high frequency of dead-weaned kids during the rainy season was observed. In addition, the results revealed that hybrid kids born during the dry season months are more vulnerable. In this case, breastfeeding and food quality during the dry season would be suspected. Thus, the programming of births and food adequacy of mothers during the dry season is essential.

Body Measurements

Body measurement data were taken from Indigenous kids and Boer crossbred kids at 9 months of age. The results presented in Table 3 revealed that the thoracic circumference (TC), height at withers (HW), body length (BL), and chest depth (CD) of Boer crossbred kids are significantly greater ($p < 0.05$) than those of Indigenous kids. Analysis of variance did not show any significant difference between male and female body measurements within each genetic group.

Table 3: Measurements of kids according to sex and genetic group at breeding age

Sources of variation	TC (cm)	HW (cm)	BL (cm)	CD (cm)
Boer crossbred kids	67.2±1.5 ^c	54.4±1.4 ^c	57.7±1.6 ^c	21.9±0.1 ^c
Indigenous kids	59.1±1.9 ^d	47.2±2.1 ^d	54.8±0.9 ^d	19.6±0.7 ^d
Boer crossbred kids female	66.5 ±0.4 ^a	51.4±1.2 ^a	56.1±1.3 ^a	21.3±0.6 ^a
Boer crossbred kids male	68.0 ±2.7 ^a	57.5±1.7 ^a	59.2± 1.8 ^a	22.6±1.3 ^a
Indigenous kids female	58.9 ±2.6 ^b	46.3±1.5 ^b	53.4 ±0.3 ^b	19.3±0.6 ^b
Indigenous kids male	59.3 ±1.2 ^b	48.0±2.6 ^b	56.3±1.6 ^b	19.8±0.8 ^b

TC=thoracic circumference, HW=height at withers, BL=body length and CD=chest depth

^{abc} The values of the same column bearing different exponents are significantly different at $p < 5\%$.

Measurements carried out on the 9-month-old Boer crossbred kids were significantly higher than those of the native kids. Usually, measurements such as HW and BL of F1 crossbred goats are always higher than those of native goats (Demeker *et al.*, 2004). The average values of the linear measurements carried out on the indigenous kids, in particular TC = 59.1 ± 1.9 cm, HW = 47.2 ± 2.1 cm, the BL = 54.8 ± 0.9 cm and CD = 19.6±0.7 cm showed that the latter belong to the "East African dwarf goat" type breed (Traoré *et al.*, 2006). However, measurements taken on the Billy kids do not differ significantly ($p > 0.05$) from those taken on the female kids even though the morphological traits of the Billy kids are relatively superior. These results corroborate the observation of Otoikhian *et al.* (2008). For some authors, sex does not significantly affect weight gain or other morphological parameters of goats. In addition, linear body measurements of hybrid males are generally higher than those of females beyond 12 months of age (Traoré *et al.*, 2006, An-Kuo Su *et al.*, 2012).

In contrast, a study conducted in central Burundi reports that the live weight and the different measurements of females are significantly higher than those of males from the age of 4 years (Manirakiza *et al.*, 2020b). Thus, the

program of crossing local goats with purebred Boer goats must involve the rigorous selection of large-size adult females to improve weight gain and different body measurements of their offspring.

Conclusion

The results obtained showed that the introduction of Billy Boer and their crosses with indigenous goats in the densely populated regions of northern Burundi considerably improved the morphological characteristics of the goat's type "East African dwarf goat". Indeed, the mean values such as live weight and height-related parameters of hybrid Boer goats turn out to be significantly higher than those of native breed goats. Nevertheless, the Boer crossbred kids showed their limits of adaptability or resistance to diseases given their high mortality both pre-weaning and post-weaning. Ultimately, cross-breeding programs of Boer goats and local goats could only be beneficial if they take place in a well-controlled breeding system and after a rigorous selection of large-size adult native females.

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Contribution by Authors

Equal contribution. All authors declared that 'written informed' consent was obtained from the approved parties for the publication of this article and accompanying images.

Conflict of Interests

There is no conflict of interest.

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